

The banner features a blue background with a complex, glowing circuit-like pattern of lines and nodes. The text 'CORENEXT' is in large, bold, white letters, with the 'X' having a blue-to-white gradient. Below it, '#13 Newsletter' is in a slightly smaller white font, and 'Holidays Library' is in an even smaller white font.

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#13 Newsletter

Holidays Library

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COREnext Holiday Library

18.12.2025 | corenext.eu

In this issue, we invite you to explore the COREnext Holiday Library, a curated overview of recent project outputs. The selection includes two of our latest scientific publications, a concise article bringing together COREnext research papers, a dedicated White Paper, and a brief overview of project demonstrations. A compact way to revisit key results and insights from COREnext over the past months.

We also take this opportunity to wish you a pleasant holiday break and all the best for the year ahead.

COREnext Latest Publications

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#COREnextInScience

[Ultra-Broadband Frequency Multiplier \(x8\) Chain in 90-nm SiGe BiCMOS Technology at H-band](#)

This work presents an H-band (220–325 GHz) frequency octupler realized in a 90-nm SiGe BiCMOS process. The 3-dB bandwidth is between 234–305 GHz, resulting in a fractional bandwidth of 26.3 %. The multiplier achieves a conversion gain between 230–310 GHz. The peak output power is -0.5 dBm, using an input power of -5 dBm. The DC power consumption is 122 mW. This type of circuit is suitable for future communication and radar systems.

[Read more](#)

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#COREnextInScience

[An Energy-Efficient 56-Gb/s D-band TX-to-RX Link using CMOS ICs and Transmitarray Antennas](#)

This paper presents an energy-efficient system with a transmitter and a receiver comprising multi-channel integrated circuits in 45-nm CMOS technology, in-package antenna feeds and high-directivity planar lenses. Data-rates up to 56 Gb/s are demonstrated over a 1-m point-to-point link using a full-digital communication system. The active circuits integrate multi-LO generators

for implementing a channel-aggregation architecture that provides a large RF bandwidth using a significantly narrower baseband interface bandwidth. The energy consumption of the overall RF system is only 33 pJ/bit.

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[Distrusting cores by separating computation from isolation](#)

In this paper, we propose the untrusted core isolation model to protect critical computation on trusted cores from untrusted and potentially buggy cores. We survey how current architectural building blocks such as MMUs fall short of this goal and derive requirements for untrusted core isolation. To demonstrate its feasibility, we discuss both changes to commodity platforms and show how research works such as M3 fulfill the requirements. We evaluate the security benefits via a qualitative comparison of current architectures in both industry and academia and study its costs by a quantitative comparison of the most promising approaches on off-the-shelf and FPGA-based platforms.

[Read more](#)

COREnext Collection

COREnext Scientific Output: Key Publications Advancing Research in Connectivity, Computing and Sub- THz Technologies

Throughout the COREnext project, partners produced a substantial body of scientific work that reflects the breadth of research carried out across communications engineering, semiconductor design, embedded systems, security and computing architectures. In total, **37 scientific papers** were published, including conference papers, journal articles, a poster abstract, a book chapter and a white paper. Together, they demonstrate both the depth and continuity of the project's scientific contributions.

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COREnext White Paper

Trustworthiness – The Key to Europe’s Digital Future

This white paper elaborates on digitalisation from a trust and security perspective and illustrates how this societal evolution will impact Europe’s current leading position in high-end consumer goods. It is clear today that the value content of products is redefined by adding connectivity and sensing capabilities to enter consumers’ digital ecosystems.

[Read more](#)

Demonstrations In A Nutshell!

TrustEvaluation and IoT Management demo

The demo showcases how the Trust Manager evaluates IoT devices in real time using trust metrics, updating each device's trust index dynamically. Based on these values and resource availability, the Trust Manager Orchestrator assigns tasks to the most reliable and capable devices, ensuring secure and efficient operation.

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The Trust Evaluation Function calculates a trust score (0 to 1) for each device class by normalising key metrics, applying weights based on importance, and adjusting for data age using exponential decay. This ensures recent data has greater influence, with the final score derived from a weighted average of the adjusted metrics.

WORKING TOWARDS END-TO-END TRUSTWORTHINESS

COREnext believes that trustworthiness needs to be a native part of 6G as anticipated applications will merge the digital and physical worlds.

The goal of the project is to strengthen the mobile communication ecosystem in Europe by addressing key challenges associated with beyond 5G use cases.

Activities stretch from radio hardware innovation to compute architectures – with trustworthiness in focus.

European core technologies for the next generation- communication- computing hardware

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Eavesdropper avoidance **imec**

This sub-THz demonstrator showcases how beam-steering technology can be used to enhance link security. The system focuses on preventing eavesdropping by dynamically controlling signal direction. It offers an interactive experience for users to engage directly with the beam-steering process.

The system integrates MATLAB baseband signal processing with analogue beam-steering transceivers, featuring four independent RF front-ends and antennas for real-time beam control. An interactive interface enables live visual monitoring and operation.

Beam-steering at sub-THz frequencies enhances link security by lowering interception risks. Real-time user interaction demonstrates practical beam control, improving public understanding of physical-layer security and offering a scalable solution for future high-frequency wireless networks.

The demo shows how real-time beam-steering at sub-THz frequencies enhances link security, offering hands-on insight into practical physical-layer cybersecurity for future networks.

RF Fingerprint for Wireless Network Security **ERICSSON**

The Radio Fingerprint demonstrator offers an interactive look at how AI can use subtle hardware impairments in radio devices to enhance cellular communication security. By learning these unique signatures, machine learning models can identify authorised transmitters and detect unauthorised access attempts.

The demo uses machine learning models trained on transmitter non-idealities to classify radio devices in real time. It employs real hardware to transmit authentication signals and identifies authorised devices based on physical signal characteristics, without decoding the data.

The system enables device identification using hardware-specific features, without cryptographic keys. It lowers the risk of unauthorised access from devices with identical chipsets and provides a low-complexity, efficient method to enhance physical-layer security.

The demonstration introduces RF fingerprinting and shows how machine learning can authenticate radio devices securely and efficiently. It highlights how physical-layer security can complement traditional cryptography to strengthen wireless network trustworthiness.

Secure Acceleration (FPGA) **NOKIA**

The Secure Acceleration demonstrator showcases FPGA-based hardware acceleration for improved digital platform efficiency. It allows multiple tenants to securely share resources, using cryptographic components and key exchange protocols to protect sensitive data, such as health information, during processing.

The FPGA acceleration board supports secure multi-tenant resource sharing, featuring cryptographic modules and secure key exchange protocols. It enables real-time, privacy-preserving data processing in sensitive areas such as healthcare.

High datarate interconnects over plastic fiber **infineon**

This demo is based on the concept of high speed data link for communication via PMF in the H-Band, and PMF coupler in package at H-Band.

- MMICs in eWLB package, assembled on PCB
- H-band PMF coupler realized in package
- H-band PMF fiber and holder

This is the first in-package PMF coupler demonstrated in the H-Band, offering a compact, low-loss, and cost-effective solution for high-speed data links. It enables faster communication with reduced energy consumption, supporting future applications such as next-generation data centres.

The goal of the demonstration is to prove the concept of communication via PMF in H-Band.

Trustworthy Computer Platform M³ **barkhausen institut**

M³, developed at Barkhausen Institut, is a modular and secure operating system built on a tiled hardware architecture. Each component runs on a separate, isolated tile, following a security-by-design approach that limits the impact of potential compromises. This architecture enhances containment of untrusted software and hardware, strengthening trust in connected systems.

The platform provides hardware-level isolation between processing components in heterogeneous systems, enabling secure execution environments that mitigate hardware-induced vulnerabilities. Its adaptable architecture supports diverse, multi-vendor system configurations.

The architecture enhances system resilience by containing faults within individual hardware modules and reducing the risk of system-wide compromise through trusted execution zones. It supports secure, scalable design essential for future digital infrastructure.

The objective of this demonstration is to illustrate how hardware isolation strengthens the trustworthiness of complex digital systems. The M³ platform demonstrates a practical method for securing next-generation platforms by compartmentalising potential risks at the hardware level.

The demonstrator enables efficient and secure hardware acceleration for multiple users or applications, ensuring data confidentiality with robust cryptographic protection. It illustrates scalable, secure resource management for future digital infrastructures.

The goal of the demonstration is to show how sensitive data can be securely processed within shared hardware environments. It highlights a crucial advancement towards secure, efficient computing for digital platforms requiring hardware acceleration in multi-tenant, high-security contexts.

[Explore our brochure where all 6 demonstrations are described!](#)

COREnext believes that trustworthiness needs to be a native part of 6G as anticipated applications will merge the digital and physical worlds. The goal of the project is to strengthen the mobile communication ecosystem in Europe by addressing key challenges associated with beyond 5G use cases. Activities stretch from radio hardware innovation to compute architectures – with trustworthiness in focus.

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Happy Holidays

& SAFE NEW YEAR

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CORENEXT is an EU-funded initiative that will bring together expert stakeholders in future mobile networks and integrate their perspectives in key focus areas like digital, analogue, and integrated solutions for computing, communication, and sensing.

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